

2024 Fall Meeting

16th - 19th September - Warsaw University of Technology - Poland

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

We certify hereby that

Julian PUSZKIEL

Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon

Geesthach

Germany

has attended the E-MRS 2024 FALL MEETING & EXHIBIT held at the University of Technology in Warsaw (Poland) from September 16 to 19.

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